

Synthesis and Pharmacology of 2-Aryl-5-Aryloxyalkyl-s-Triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-Thiadiazoles

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A number of new s-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles carrying aryl moiety at 2 position and aryloxyalkyl group at 5 position were synthesised and evaluated for their pharmacological activity. Some compounds exhibited strong CNS depressant, mild hypocholesterolemic and hypotensive action in experimental animals.

S-TRIAZOLES¹⁻⁶ and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles⁷⁻⁹ are reported to exhibit broad spectrum of biological and pesticidal activities. It is observed¹⁰ that s-triazoles fused to 1,3,4-thiadiazoles have not been explored for their biological activity. Our earlier work on the synthesis of 2-aryl-5-aryl/aryloxy-s-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles¹¹ revealed CNS depressant and mild to strong antiinflammatory activity for the compounds.

Incorporation of appropriate aryloxyalkyl moiety in the heterocyclic residues^{12,13} such as pyrroles, pyrazoles and oxadiazoles has led to the compounds possessing CNS depressant, antiinflammatory, hypocholesterolemic and hypotensive action. These findings prompted us to synthesise 2-aryl-5-aryloxyalkyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles represented by structure I with a view to explore the possibility of obtaining biologically useful compounds.

The synthesis of I was accomplished in one step by reacting 3-aryl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

with aryloxyalkyl carboxylic acids in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. The title compounds along with their pharmacological data are described in Table 1.

R = H or Cl ; R₁ and R₂ = H or CH₃
R₃ = H, CH₃ or Cl ; R₄ = H or CH₃ ; R₅ = H or Cl.

TABLE 1—2-ARYL-5-ARYLOXYALKYL-S-TRIAZOLO[3,4-b]-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	m.p. °C	% Decrease in motor activity at 100 mg/kg (i.p. mice)	Hypotensive action at 5 mg/kg mm
1.	H	H	H	H	H	H	153-5	67	-13
2.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	136-8	60	-33
3.	H	H	H	H	H	Cl	172-4	23	-
4.	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	Cl	158-60	38	-28
5.	Cl	H	H	H	H	H	183-4	38	-14
6.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	145-7	58	-
7.	Cl	H	H	H	H	Cl	185-7	32	-
8.	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	H	Cl	198-9	35	-
9.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	207-9	34	-27
10.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	Cl	153-4	46	-19
11.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Cl	170-1	35	-16
12.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	Cl	172-4	40	-33
13.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	H	Cl	171-3	45	-50
14.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	H	176-8	59	-30
15.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	Cl	170-2	55	-30
16.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	Cl	171-2	42	-28
17.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	Cl	166-8	65	-29
18.	Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	H	Cl	200-3	36	-33

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were within ±0.5% of the theoretical values.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 221 infrared spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were taken on a Varian A60A spectrometer using TMS as the external standard. Mass spectra were recorded at 70eV on a Hitachi RMU 6L Mass spectrometer. All compounds were checked for their purity on tlc plates and characterised by elemental analysis and spectral studies. 3-Aryl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles were prepared by the method of Heindel¹⁴.

2-Phenyl-5-phenoxyethyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1): A mixture of 3-phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (3.84 g; 0.02 mole), phenoxyacetic acid (3.04 g; 0.02 mole) and POCl₃ (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hr. The excess POCl₃ was removed and the mixture was poured over crushed ice. The reaction mixture was made alkaline with 10% sodium bicarbonate. The product was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1590 (aromatic C=C), 1640 (C=N) and 1240 cm⁻¹ (ether linkage). M⁺ at m/e 308.

Compounds 2-9 were synthesised in similar manner.

2-Phenyl-5-[α -(4-chlorophenoxy)isopropyl]-s-triazolo[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (10): 3-Phenyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (3.84 g; 0.02 mole), α -(4-chlorophenoxy)isobutyric acid¹⁵ (4.29 g; 0.02 mole) and POCl₃ (20 ml) were mixed and refluxed for 5 hr. The cooled reaction mixture, after removal of excess POCl₃, was poured into ice water, made alkaline by adding sodium bicarbonate solution and the resulting solid was filtered. It was recrystallised from ethanol to give the title compound. PMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.81 (s, 6H, isopropyl protons) and 7.03-7.85 (m, 9H, aromatic protons). M⁺ at m/e 370.

Compounds 11-18 were prepared in the same way.

Pharmacological evaluation: The compounds listed in Table I were subjected to primary screening in experimental animals at the Department of Pharmacology, G. S. Medical College, Bombay. Toxicity (LD₅₀), antiinflammatory, hypotensive, hypocholesterolemic and motor activities were determined by literature methods¹⁶⁻¹⁸. All the compounds were devoid of toxicity (LD₅₀ > 800

mg/kg oral p.o.). They did not exhibit promising antiinflammatory activity in comparison to phenylbutazone. Compounds 10-13 and 15-18 were screened for the hypocholesterolemic activity employing clofibrate as the control standard. Compounds 11 and 15 exhibited mild hypocholesterolemic activity. Compounds 1, 2 and 17 exhibited significant CNS depressant activity while compounds 2, 12, 13 and 18 showed appreciable hypotensive activity.

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